

Tests as Socio-Technical Artifacts: First Thoughts on its Implications for Validity Theory.

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Abstract

Tests have often been described as devices, tools or technologies, but the full implications of this characterization have not been yet explored. In this paper, I examine the consequences of understanding tests as socio-technical artifacts, drawing on insights from philosophy of technology. I argue that foundational concepts from this field—particularly around function, use-plans, and design—clarify ongoing debates about validity and fairness. These debates often stem not from epistemological differences alone, but from differing assumptions about how functions are attributed or ascribed to artifacts. I propose a novel framework for interpreting test validity through the lens of technology validation, grounded in the idea of test function. Adapting Kroes' account of technical artifacts (Kroes, 2012), I suggest that a test designed to measure construct C is valid if and only if it is the outcome of a largely successful implementation of a largely correct design for that purpose—and, as a result, qualifies as a measurer of C, meaning it belongs to the functional kind of devices that measure C. The paper concludes with a discussion of the broader implications of viewing tests as socio-technical artifacts embedded in complex systems of use.

1 Introduction

Test validity remains one of the most contested and widely discussed concepts in educational and psychological assessment. Early formulations, such as Cureton's (1951) emphasis on correlational evidence, laid the groundwork for more complex interpretations. Cronbach (1971) advanced an evaluative perspective on validity, which was later expanded by Messick's (1989a) influential articulation of a unitary concept of validity that integrates both interpretation and use, supported by evidentiary and consequential bases. Building on this foundation, Kane (1992, 2006, 2013) introduced

an argument-based approach to validation, emphasizing the logical coherence of the interpretive chain. More recently, Lane and Marion (in press) have re-centered fairness and normative considerations as core components of validation, pushing the field toward more inclusive frameworks. Alongside these developments, Borsboom and colleagues (Borsboom et al., 2004, 2009) has offered a realist critique of construct validity, while Randall and colleagues (Randall, 2021; Randall et al., 2022) have challenged traditional paradigms from the perspective of Critical Race Theory. Numerous other scholars—including Mislevy (2009, 2018), Sireci (2013, 2020a, 2020b), Cizek (2020), Moss (Moss et al., 2006), Solano-Flores (Solano-Flores & Nelson-Barber, 2001; del Rosario Basterra et al., 2011), Kūkea Shultz and Englert (2021), and Zumbo (2009, 2017, 2023)—have contributed diverse perspectives that reflect philosophical, methodological, and sociopolitical dimensions of test validity. As Newton and Shaw (2016) note, the ongoing debate underscores the richness and complexity of a construct that sits at the heart of responsible test use.

Tracing the evolution of the concept of validity (Kane, 2006; Kane & Bridgeman, 2021) —particularly following Borsboom's influential distinction between validity as a property and validation as a process (Borsboom et al., 2004) —reveals a set of foundational debates that continue to shape the field. Among these, several enduring “isms” remain unresolved. One central issue concerns the role of values in defining validity. On one side, some scholars argue that validity is a technical, value-neutral property, independent of the social, ethical, or political implications of a test and its interpretations (Borsboom & Wijsen, 2016). On the other side, a growing body of literature asserts that values are inextricably linked to both the concept of validity and the practices of validation (Messick, 1989a), particularly when considering conse-

quences, fairness, and the broader context in which assessments operate.

Another enduring ism in the validity literature concerns the role of test use. Some authors argue that validity is an intrinsic property of the test or test score, independent of how it is ultimately applied (Borsboom et al., 2004). Others maintain that validity is inherently contingent on the interpretation and use of test scores (Messick, 1989b; Kane, 2013; Lane & Marion, in press). Proponents of a leaner concept of validity—one that does not hinge on specific uses—argue that attaching validity to use introduces unnecessary subjectivity and operational complexity. In contrast, advocates for including use argue that a test cannot be meaningfully validated apart from the decisions and actions it informs. The Standards for Educational and Psychological Testing (AERA, APA & NCME, 2014) occupy a kind of middle ground, defining validation as the process of evaluating the interpretation of test scores for intended uses. This formulation is, in some ways, polysemic: it accommodates divergent philosophical positions, enabling both intrinsic and use-contingent perspectives to coexist within the same definitional space.

Divergent positions on validity often stem from underlying epistemological commitments. Maul et al. (2016) identify at least two dominant stances in the literature: a realist view, which treats validity as a property grounded in objective relationships between constructs and test scores, and a pragmatic view, which emphasizes the utility and consequences of test interpretations in real-world contexts. In addition, some perspectives align more closely with social-constructivist epistemology, explicitly framing validity as a function of negotiated meanings and sociocultural processes (Dixon-Román & Gergen, 2013). While the explicit acknowledgment of these epistemological foundations contributes to greater transparency in validity debates, it also introduces the risk of epistemic relativism. Without a shared foundation or criteria for adjudicating between competing claims, the field may struggle to develop a coherent validity theory capable of guiding practitioners in the technical and operational demands of test development and use.

This paper introduces a novel perspective into the ongoing debate on test validity. Its central thesis is that tests should be understood as socio-technical artifacts, and that questions of test validity are more appropriately situated within the philosophy

of technology rather than the traditional domain of the philosophy of science. Drawing on foundational and emerging ideas from the philosophy of technology—a relatively young but rapidly growing area within philosophical inquiry—I argue that recognizing tests as socio-technical artifacts sheds new light on longstanding debates in our field. This perspective offers a deeper conceptual grounding for understanding the validity of tests, their interpretations, and their uses. It also has the potential to reframe several unresolved tensions by offering alternative conceptual tools and frameworks. At the very least, this approach introduces new angles of discussion that may help clarify, explain, or reconcile the diverse positions held by scholars on what validity entails and how it should be theorized and applied.

Central to this thesis is the development of theories of function within the philosophy of technology. These theories offer critical insights into how the function of an artifact is defined, interpreted, and evaluated—insights that are directly applicable to understanding tests as designed artifacts. A second, closely related thesis of this paper is that many of the central debates in the validity literature can be interpreted as stemming from divergent views about the function of tests: how that function is conceptualized, what constitutes its fulfillment, and what kinds of evidence or reasoning are required to support such claims. By framing test validity through the lens of functional attribution, this paper seeks to illuminate how epistemological, ethical, and methodological disagreements in the literature often reflect deeper, and sometimes implicit, assumptions about what tests are for and how their proper functioning should be assessed.

This paper will begin with a brief introduction to the concept of technical artifacts, drawing primarily on the work of Kroes (Kroes, 2012). I will then outline several prominent theories concerning how the function of a technical artifact can be defined, again following Kroes' systematic treatment of the issue. Special attention will be given to his conception of functions as a structure-function dual, which I will expand upon by offering reflections grounded in the domain of educational testing. Building on this foundation, I will explore how these philosophical insights can inform and recontextualize the central debates in validity theory. In particular, I will propose a set of parallelisms between disputes over the proper definition of artifact function and those surrounding test validity.

As part of this discussion, I will reinterpret Kroes' notion of technical-kind attribution and adapt it to validity theory. Specifically, I will propose that a test should be considered valid if and only if it is the result of a largely successful execution of a largely correct design for a measurer of construct C. This formulation allows us to reconcile the apparent divide between viewing the test itself as the object of validity versus focusing on the interpretation and use of its scores. I argue that this divide is artificial in the sense that both are referring to different forms of function attribution: one *ex-ante* the construction of a technical artifact and one *ex-post* given certain fixed structure of a technical artifact.

Finally, I will explore the broader implications of this reconceptualization across two key areas: (1) how it informs our understanding of construct misrepresentation and types of invalidity, and (2) how it may be extended to address emerging challenges in the use of Artificial Intelligence in Measurement.

2 About Technical and Socio-Technical Artifacts

Philosophy of technology is a relatively new sub-field within philosophy, emerging more prominently in the latter half of the twentieth century. While philosophical reflection on tools and techniques dates back to antiquity, it is only in recent decades that technology has been treated as a systematic object of philosophical inquiry in its own right (Kroes, 2012). This growing field aims to understand the nature, function, and significance of technological artifacts, not merely as applications of science, but as distinct human-made entities with their own epistemological, ontological, and normative dimensions (Dusek, 2006). As Kroes notes, one of the driving motivations behind this field is the recognition that technology, far from being a neutral backdrop to human action, fundamentally shapes the conditions of human life, thought, and society (Kroes, 2012; p. 1). This shift in focus—from seeing technology as derivative of science to recognizing its unique conceptual and practical features—has led to the development of theories that account for the dual nature of technical artifacts, bridging the physical and intentional dimensions that characterize their creation and use. As such, the philosophy of technology not only seeks to clarify what technology is, but also to provide tools for evaluating its role and implications

in our world.

Philosophy of technology concerns itself with understanding the nature, function, and implications of technology as a distinct domain of human activity. Rather than treating technology as a mere application of scientific knowledge, it interrogates what makes technological artifacts unique, how they come into being, and what roles they play in shaping the human condition (Dusek, 2006). Central to this field are questions about the ontological status of technical artifacts—what kind of objects they are and how they differ from natural or purely social entities. It also engages with epistemological questions: how we come to know and understand technological systems, and how such knowledge differs from scientific theory. Additionally, the field addresses normative issues such as the ethical significance of design choices, the responsibility of engineers, and the moral agency of artifacts themselves (Kroes, 2012). As Kroes emphasizes, a key challenge is to reconcile the dual nature of technical artifacts: they are simultaneously physical constructions and intentional creations, embodying both material constraints and human purposes (Kroes, 2012; pp. 5–6). This hybrid status demands conceptual frameworks that can bridge the divide between physical causality and intentionality, making the philosophy of technology uniquely interdisciplinary and foundational for modern technological societies.

Philosophy of technology intersects with philosophy of science in the exploration of technoscience, a concept that captures the increasing entanglement of scientific inquiry and technological development. Technoscience refers to domains in which scientific practices are deeply embedded within technological systems, and where the boundaries between discovering and making, explaining and designing, begin to blur. In contrast to the classical view that sees science as aimed at understanding the world and technology as applying that knowledge, the concept of technoscience challenges this separation by revealing how contemporary scientific practices are often dependent on technological instrumentation, methods, and goals (Kroes, 2012; Chapter 5.2). As Kroes notes, in engineering and design processes, scientific reasoning is often interwoven with practical problem-solving and instrumental rationality, producing knowledge that is not purely explanatory but also inherently constructive (Kroes, 2012; pp. 131–135). In this light, technoscience reflects a shift in epistemology and ontology, where

the creation of artifacts is not merely downstream from theory, but becomes a mode of knowing in itself. This convergence further strengthens the case for treating technical artifacts—and their functions—not just as outcomes of scientific work, but as central elements in how we produce, structure, and validate knowledge in the modern world.

An artifact is generally understood as an object made or significantly modified by humans to fulfill a particular purpose. The term itself, derived from the Latin *arte factum*—meaning "made by skill"—implies intentional human creation. In Kroes' framework, artifacts are distinguished from natural objects by their origin in human activity and their purpose-driven character (Kroes, 2012; p. 2). Artifacts do not simply exist; they are brought into being through acts of making that involve both mental (design, intention) and physical (fabrication, assembly) processes. This dual origin underscores their hybrid nature as both creations of the mind and configurations of matter. Examples of artifacts include simple tools like hammers and screwdrivers, complex devices such as computers and automobiles, and even infrastructural systems like power grids or traffic lights (Kroes, 2012; Chapter 2.1). Some artifacts may also border on the social or symbolic—for instance, currency, contracts, or digital user interfaces—but Kroes narrows the philosophical analysis to material technical artifacts, those created for practical use and realized through physical construction. These include items that are intentionally designed to solve practical problems and whose function is tied closely to their structure, setting the foundation for their study within the philosophy of technology.

A technical artifact is a specific kind of artifact—one that is intentionally designed and physically constructed to fulfill a practical function in response to human needs. According to Kroes, technical artifacts are material objects created through engineering or technological processes and are distinct from natural objects (which arise without human intervention) and from purely social artifacts (which may exist as abstract entities, like laws or contracts) (Kroes, 2012; pp. 13–14). What sets technical artifacts apart is their "for-ness"—that is, they are for doing something in particular, such as cutting, measuring, or transporting (Kroes, 2012; p. 4). This for-ness is not merely about use, but about the intentionality embedded in their design. For example, a knife is for cutting, a printer is for producing documents, and a thermometer is

for measuring temperature. These objects not only have physical structures but are also embedded with functional roles that connect them to human purposes. Other examples of technical artifacts include clocks, cars, staplers, bridges, and computers—all of which are conceived through design and realized through material construction in order to solve specific practical problems. As Kroes emphasizes, technical artifacts thus possess a dual nature: they are simultaneously physical objects and intentional constructs, making them a central subject in the philosophy of technology (Kroes, 2012; pp. 5–6).

A socio-technical artifact is an object or system whose function and existence emerge from the interaction between technical components and social structures. Unlike purely technical artifacts—which are defined by their material construction and practical function—socio-technical artifacts incorporate human roles, institutional norms, and collective practices into their operation and meaning (Kroes, 2012; pp. 15–16). Their functionality cannot be fully explained by physical mechanisms alone; it also depends on social recognition, conventions, and coordination. For instance, a traffic light system is not merely a technical device but part of a broader socio-technical system that includes traffic laws, driver behavior, and enforcement practices. Other examples include automated voting machines, digital payment systems, public transportation networks, and even online educational platforms. Each of these artifacts functions through a blend of technological design and social infrastructure. As Kroes points out, some practical problems are not solved by technology alone but by socio-technical systems—solutions that combine technical artifacts with social roles and rules to achieve coordinated outcomes (Kroes, 2012; pp. 16–17). Thus, socio-technical artifacts highlight the inseparability of human and machine agency in many aspects of modern life, making them essential to a comprehensive understanding of technology in context.

Educational and psychological tests are a highly specific type of socio-technical artifact, distinguished by their intricate blending of material, conceptual, and institutional components. A test is an artifact in the sense that it is intentionally designed by humans to serve a purpose—namely, to generate information about individuals' knowledge, abilities, or psychological traits. It qualifies as a technical artifact—at least in part—because it consists of structured elements such as items, scoring rubrics,

answer sheets, software platforms, and statistical models. These components are engineered to function reliably and systematically within psychometric frameworks, often with the goal of measurement or classification. However, a test is also, and perhaps more crucially, a socio-technical artifact, as its meaning, function, and effectiveness cannot be understood independently of the social systems that surround it. The interpretation of test scores, the legitimacy of its use, and the impact it has on individuals and institutions depend on policies, cultural norms, professional practices, and ethical standards. The test functions only insofar as it is embedded in and sustained by a network of social roles—test-takers, educators, test developers, policymakers—each of whom interacts with the artifact in specific ways. Importantly, the boundaries of the test as a system are often blurry. This ambiguity, which complicates validation efforts and system accountability, is partly inherited from classical systems theory, where inputs, outputs, and system-environment distinctions were treated as relatively fixed and unproblematic constructs. In reality, the “test” encompasses a shifting and permeable set of devices, institutions, and interpretations—making it a paradigmatic case of a socio-technical artifact with contested boundaries and evolving functions. In this paper, I understand a test closer to what Drasgow et al. (2006) describe as a “system of systems.”

In conceptualizing tests, it becomes necessary to recognize multiple overlapping categories in which a test simultaneously exists. First, tests can be understood as technical artifacts, in that they are engineered structures composed of items, formats, scoring procedures, and delivery mechanisms, all designed to function in a reliable and reproducible manner (Kroes, 2012). Second, they may be framed as measurement artifacts—that is, devices whose primary function is to measure a latent property or attribute. This functional designation aligns tests with rulers, thermometers, or scales, but with a critical difference: tests often operate at the intersection of symbolic representation and behavioral observation. Third, within this broader class, psychological and educational measurement artifacts constitute a more specialized subset. Here, the function is not only to measure, but to measure constructs about persons—such as ability, motivation, or knowledge—constructs that are themselves the product of evolving theories in psychology and education. These constructs are

not given in nature but are theorized and modeled, often in probabilistic terms, through psychometric or cognitive frameworks. When the targeted constructs are not observable, we fall within a very specific use-case for measurement devices, in which we are also making a form of inference about an unobservable. For example, the James Webb Telescope measures observables but it is also intended to make inferences about unobservable characteristics about planets. This form of latent measurement is customary along the educational and psychological tests we know.

Despite these layered classifications, there is a clear and persistent overlap between tests and technical artifacts. Tests are not neutral or passive carriers of theory; they are actively engineered to support particular interpretations and uses. At the very least, a test is designed to enable specific inferences, which are embedded within its structure. This functional intentionality grounds tests squarely within the realm of technical design—even as their meaning and value extend far into social, theoretical, and ethical domains.

3 Theories of Technical Artifact Function

The philosophy of technology defines the function of a technical artifact as the feature that connects its physical structure to its intended use in solving a practical problem. The function of a technical artifact is usually associated with a verb (to cut, to print, to measure) and it is a property of the artifact (potentially, a relational property tightened to context). If X is a technical artifact and ϕ is a verb, the underling claim here is “The function of X is to ϕ .”

According to Kroes, the function of a technical artifact is not merely a description of what the artifact does, but a normative claim about what it is for—a claim that reflects both human intention and physical realization (Kroes, 2012; pp. 4–6). In this view, function is a bridge concept that links the intentional and physical domains: it is determined by human purposes but must be realizable through the artifact’s material structure. Kroes elaborates this in his structure-function conception, where a technical artifact is defined by a dual nature: it is a physical object designed to fulfill a function, and this function is both causally dependent on its structure and conceptually dependent on human goals (Kroes, 2012; Chapter 2.4). For example, a screwdriver’s function—to drive screws—depends not

only on its shape and material properties but also on its being intended for that purpose. Without the alignment of physical capacity and human purpose, a mere object remains just that—an object—not a technical artifact. Thus, function in the philosophy of technology is not reducible to causal effects or user practices alone, but is an integrated concept that entails design intention, normative use, and structural feasibility.

The philosophy of technology makes an important conceptual distinction between function attribution and function ascription, particularly in discussions about the nature of technical artifacts. Function attribution refers to the claim that an object has a certain function based on its physical structure and capacities—for instance, stating that a screwdriver is for driving screws because of its shape and mechanical properties. The underlying claim here is “X is a phi-er” an object meant so its function is to phi. For example, this knife is a cutter, this thermometer is a measurer of temperature, etc. This view often aligns with more realist or structuralist accounts of function, where the function is seen as inherent to the object due to what it can reliably do (Kroes, 2012; Chapter 3.2).

In contrast, function ascription refers to the act of assigning a function to an object based on human intentions, goals, or social practices. The underlying claim here is “X is for phi-ing.” For example, a person might ascribe the function of a paperweight to a stone, even though it was not designed for that purpose. The function in this case is given ex-post its creation, and may not necessarily change the nature of the object itself but just describing the space of actions possible from its structure. This view emphasizes the intentional and contextual aspects of function, and is often associated with mind-dependent or constructivist theories of artifacts (Kroes, 2012; Chapter 3.4).

The distinction is relevant, because an object that has something we could call “proper function”, meaning, it was designed to Phi, may be used in other contexts for other actions and that not make it a different class of object. For example, a bread knife can be used as a screwdriver for some cases, but this is accidental and not worthy to change the whole definition of what we understand and expect from an object labeled as a ‘screwdriver’ to accommodate the case of a knife that can be used for driving screws in some cases. Kroes makes the case that “X is a Phi-er” implies “X is for phi-ing” but not the reverse.

3.1 Explaining Different Theories

Different theories of function diverge in how they treat this distinction. Ontological theories tend to focus on attribution and argue that functions are real properties grounded in the object’s physical makeup and evolutionary or design history. In contrast, epistemic or pragmatic theories emphasize ascription, viewing function as context-dependent and reliant on users’ interpretations or social roles. Hybrid theories—such as the one proposed by Kroes—attempt to reconcile these positions by arguing that a full account of technical function must recognize both the structural realization of function and the intentional, normative dimension that gives it meaning (Kroes, 2012; pp. 59–63). Understanding this distinction is crucial for analyzing artifacts like tests, whose function depends both on their technical structure and on their use within broader social and institutional frameworks.

3.2 Cummins’ Causal View

There are numerous perspectives on what function is and how it should be operationalized in the creation of technology. These perspectives differ in how they conceptualize the relationship between human intention, artifact structure, and use. A foundational account of function, particularly influential in both philosophy of biology and technology, is the causal-role theory developed by Robert Cummins (1975). In this view, functions are not determined by historical origins or normative expectations, but by the causal contributions that components make to the capacities of the systems they are part of. Cummins establishes three key conditions for a function attribution: (1) the item must be part of a larger system; (2) it must play a causal role in enabling some capacity or behavior of that system; and (3) this role must be identified through a functional analysis, where the system’s higher-level capacity is decomposed into sub-capacities performed by its parts. Crucially, this framework treats function as relative to the analytical context: what counts as a function depends on the explanatory goals and the system under study.

While Cummins’ causal-role theory offers a compellingly neutral and system-oriented view of function, it faces important limitations when applied to technical artefacts. As Kroes (2012) argues, a key problem is causal promiscuity—the tendency of artefacts to have multiple causal effects within a

system, only some of which are relevant to their intended or proper function. A hammer, for instance, may both drive nails and produce noise, but only the former is typically considered its function. The causal account lacks the resources to distinguish which effects matter without invoking normative or intentional criteria. Moreover, Kroes emphasizes that technical artefacts are mind-dependent entities: their functions are inherently tied to human intentions, cultural practices, and socially embedded use plans. A purely causal account neglects this dependence and risks treating artefacts as if their functions were discovered rather than ascribed. Without acknowledging the designer's intent or the user's interpretive framework, the causal-role theory cannot fully capture the teleological character of technologies, nor explain why some causal contributions count as functions while others do not.

3.3 Searle's Status Functions

One influential view is offered by John Searle (1995), who frames functions in terms of status functions—functions that depend entirely on collective intentionality. According to Searle, an object has a function if a community assigns it a role within a system of social recognition. For example, a piece of paper is money only because we collectively treat it as such. In this view, the function of a technical artifact is constituted by its assignment of purpose within a framework of social rules and collective acceptance, rather than by any intrinsic physical property or causal role (Kroes, 2012, pp. 63–68). While this account effectively highlights the socially constructed nature of many technical artefacts, especially those embedded in institutional systems (e.g., passports, thermostats, traffic lights), Kroes argues that it falls short when it comes to explaining how artefacts actually realize their functions in practice. His critique points out that Searle's framework lacks a mechanism for linking the assigned function to the physical structure and capabilities of the artefact itself. In other words, Searle explains why something is treated as having a function, but not how it is able to perform that function. Without accounting for the interplay between material realization and functional use, the status-function approach risks reducing technical artefacts to mere symbolic or institutional objects, ignoring the material and operational dimensions that are essential to their role in the world.

3.4 Preston's Proper Functions

Preston (1998, 2012) advocates for a biological or proper-function approach, emphasizing analogies to evolutionary biology. In her view, an artifact's proper function is not merely what it is used for, but the specific function for which it was originally selected, designed, or maintained—much like organs in a biological organism evolve because they contribute to the survival and reproductive success of the organism as a whole. This perspective treats artifacts as components within broader systems—technological, social, or biological—that exert selective pressure over time. Just as a heart is said to have the function of pumping blood because that activity contributed to the survival of ancestral organisms, a hammer is said to have the function of driving nails because that use has been historically reinforced and maintained through its effectiveness. The normativity of function, in this account, arises from this history of selective success: an artifact is supposed to perform the function it was selected for, particularly under ideal conditions. Preston's approach thus grounds functional attributions in evolutionary-like processes, allowing for a naturalized understanding of normativity that does not rely solely on explicit intentions or momentary uses (Kroes, 2012, pp. 69–75).

3.5 Houkes and Vermaas' ICE Theory

Another prominent account is the ICE theory developed by Houkes and Vermaas (2010), which stands for Intentional, Causal-role, and Evolutionary conditions. This theory provides a nuanced analysis of technical functions by integrating three distinct yet interrelated dimensions. The Intentional condition asserts that artifacts have functions because they are intentionally designed by agents with specific purposes in mind. The Causal-role condition emphasizes the actual physical contributions the artifact makes within a system, akin to the way organs serve roles in biological systems. The Evolutionary condition introduces a historical and normative dimension: it requires that the function be embedded in a tradition of reproduction, imitation, or maintenance that reinforces its intended use over time. Together, these three conditions ensure that a function is not merely attributed arbitrarily, but can be ascribed based on a structured, repeatable, and socially stabilized context of use. The ICE theory thus aims to bridge the gap between function ascription (based on human intentions) and

function attribution (based on observed behavior or performance), offering a robust framework that accommodates both teleological and mechanistic understandings of technical artifacts.

Central to the ICE framework is the concept of a use plan, which serves as a crucial bridge between an artefact's intended function and its practical deployment. A use plan is a structured set of prescriptions or guidelines that specify how an artefact is meant to be used in order to realize its designed function. It includes the actions that users must perform, the conditions under which those actions are effective, and the goals that those actions are supposed to achieve. In this sense, a use plan operationalizes the intentional dimension of the ICE theory, embedding purpose into a repeatable pattern of interaction. Importantly, use plans are not merely private intentions; they are often socially shared, taught, and embedded in cultural practices, making them both normative and transferable. By linking user behavior with the artefact's physical capacities and design history, use plans help stabilize function attributions across different contexts and users. They thus play a pivotal role in explaining how artefacts maintain functional identity over time, even as they are used by different agents in varied settings (Houkes & Vermaas, 2010; Kroes, 2012).

Each of these perspectives operationalizes function differently—whether as a social assignment grounded in collective intentionality (Searle), a teleological-historical property tied to evolutionary design and use history (Preston), a causal contribution within a system (Cummins), or a structured interaction of intentions, physical capacities, and socio-historical contexts (Houkes & Vermaas, 2010). While each offers valuable insights, Kroes (2012) argues that none of these accounts, taken in isolation, fully resolves the dual nature of technical artifacts—their simultaneous existence as material constructs and as intentional, normatively loaded objects. Searle's theory, for instance, highlights the socially constructed nature of functions but neglects how these functions are materially realized; it explains why something counts as having a function, but not how it actually performs that function. Preston's evolutionary approach grounds function in successful design history but struggles to accommodate newly invented or reappropriated artefacts whose functional legitimacy does not yet rest on repeated use. Cummins's causal-role theory, while elegantly descriptive, fails to account for normativ-

ity—why some causal effects are considered the function and others mere byproducts. Even the ICE theory, though it explicitly integrates intentional, causal, and evolutionary dimensions, tends to rely heavily on pre-existing frameworks of design and replication, which may not be present in cases of one-off inventions or radically novel technologies. As Kroes emphasizes, understanding function in the context of technology creation demands a pluralistic or hybrid account—one that captures the complex interplay between physical structure, user and designer intentions, and the social norms that embed artefacts in collective practices. Only by embracing this integrated view can we do justice to the ontological and epistemological richness of technical function.

4 Connections Between Test Validity and Theories for Technical Artifact Functions

Long-standing controversies in test validity theory can be understood as reflections of deeper philosophical debates about the nature of function, particularly as explored in the philosophy of technology. Central to both domains is the question of what it means for something to function as it ought, whether that be a test or a technical artifact. In this light, Borsboom's causal theory of validity—which asserts that a test is valid if the psychological construct it purports to measure exists and causally produces variation in test scores (Borsboom et al., 2004)—finds a strong parallel in Cummins' causal-role account of function. Cummins argues that a component's function lies in the causal contribution it makes to the capacity of a larger system, independent of historical or intentional factors. Both perspectives adopt a realist stance, assuming that constructs (in psychometrics) or system capacities (in technology) are mind-independent phenomena that can be identified through appropriate analytical decomposition. As such, they resist relativistic, use-based, or intention-dependent definitions. The emphasis, in both views, is on structural correspondence and causal efficacy: the test must accurately reflect the construct's operation, just as an artifact must reliably perform its designated role within a system.

Interestingly, the same criticisms directed at purely causal accounts of function attribution and ascription in the philosophy of technology also apply to Borsboom's causal theory of test validity.

One prominent issue is that of causal promiscuity: if we strictly follow Borsboom's criterion—that a test is valid if the construct exists and causally produces variation in test scores—then almost any causal relationship could imply validity. For instance, a K-12 mathematics test might be deemed valid for measuring math anxiety, simply because anxiety causally influences test performance. This echoes the challenge in function theory where artefacts produce many causal effects, but only some are considered functions. Philosophy of technology offers a useful distinction here—between causal views of function attribution (what a tool does) and views of function ascription tied to correct design under mind-dependent purposes. A test, like any technical artifact, exists within a reality shaped by human intentions and use contexts—what some might call an augmented reality—where the meaning and appropriateness of its function depend on collective understanding. This dual nature of tests—as mind-dependent technologies used to measure potentially mind-independent constructs—creates a fundamental tension. It may well be one of the core reasons why the field of educational measurement continues to struggle with reaching a stable and unified account of validity.

Kane's argument-based approach to validation (Kane, 1992, 2013) aligns closely with epistemic and pragmatic theories of function in the philosophy of technology—particularly those that prioritize justification through reasoning over metaphysical claims about intrinsic properties. In this framework, the validity of a test is not a fixed or inherent quality but the outcome of a well-supported interpretive argument that justifies the use of test scores for specific purposes. This approach resonates with Searle's concept of status functions, where the function of an artifact—or a social object like a test—is not discovered in its material structure, but assigned within a system of collective intentionality and rule-governed practices. Just as a piece of paper becomes money because a community collectively agrees to treat it as such, a test gains validity through consensus around its intended use, supported by coherent and evidence-based reasoning. This connection becomes clearer when we consider that, in both cases, the function is not ontologically inherent but emerges from a normative framework—one that depends on shared practices, explicit justifications, and ongoing scrutiny. In this sense, Kane's validity theory mirrors function ascription in technical artifacts: both require a persua-

sive rationale that links design and interpretation to intended outcomes, and both emphasize legitimacy through argument rather than through causal mechanisms alone. The test, like the technical artifact, succeeds when the chain of reasoning connecting its use to its claims is robust, transparent, and socially accepted.

Theories of action (Bennett, 2010)—particularly those grounded in intentionality, goal-directed behavior, and instrumentality—are closely related to models of function ascription in the philosophy of technology. In both domains, actions and functions are means to an end, shaped by intentions, norms, and expectations about outcomes. A technical artifact functions properly when it enables or supports a successful action, just as an action is considered rational or appropriate when it effectively advances an intended goal. This perspective also offers a natural bridge to evolutionary accounts of function, such as Preston's (1998, 2012), who argues that artefacts have proper functions because they have been selected or maintained within systems that depend on their use for achieving larger objectives. Seen through this lens, tests can be understood as instrumental actions embedded within broader social, institutional, and educational ecosystems—they are not standalone tools, but parts of evolving systems whose continued existence depends on the success of their functions. A test survives and becomes entrenched not just because it measures something, but because it contributes to larger goal-oriented structures, such as admission systems, credentialing, or accountability policies. This framing aligns with Kroes' assertion that technical functions are inseparable from user intentions and practical contexts, and recasts validity as a question of functional integration: does the test contribute to the system's survival, coherence, and purpose? In this sense, theories of action illuminate the embedded, system-sustaining role of assessment tools, making validity a reflection of their evolutionary fitness within human-designed, socially sustained action structures.

Few practitioners in educational measurement have explicitly drawn on the ICE theory framework as developed by Houkes and Vermaas (2010), which integrates Intentional, Causal-role, and Evolutionary conditions for understanding function. However, a notable and promising parallel appears in the work cited by Oliveri et al. (2020), particularly in their application of a three-level framework—Construction, Logic, and Conse-

quences—to college admissions testing. Although not directly framed in ICE terminology, each of these levels implicitly aligns with a component of the ICE theory. The Construction level addresses the intentional design of the assessment system, corresponding to the Intentional condition. The Logic level engages with the internal structure and inferential reasoning connecting test scores to interpretations, echoing the Causal-role condition. Finally, the Consequences level considers the broader impact and long-term integration of the test in educational and social systems, which resonates with the Evolutionary dimension of ICE.

In general, Evidence-Centered Design (ECD; Mislevy et al., 2003) is conceptually aligned with design-based theories of technical artifact function—particularly those that emphasize the relationship between intentional design, structural implementation, and functional success. In ECD, the test is viewed as a structured argument, designed from the outset to support specific inferences about a construct, based on observable evidence. This mirrors Kroes’ structure-function conception, where a technical artifact is defined by the intentional transformation of matter to fulfill a practical purpose (Kroes, 2012; Chapter 2.4). In both frameworks, design is central: an artifact—or a test—is valid or functional to the extent that it successfully realizes a design aimed at producing interpretable outcomes. ECD’s layered modeling approach (including the construct model, evidence model, and task model) is akin to engineering workflows, where abstract functional requirements are progressively translated into physical form. Moreover, the validation logic in ECD, which ensures alignment between evidence and intended interpretation, corresponds closely to Kroes’ view that technical artifacts must exhibit a form of structure-function coherence in order to be considered successful realizations of their kind. Thus, ECD not only supports a functionalist view of validity, but does so in a way that integrates intentions, structures, and evidence-generating behavior—the same triad that defines technical artifact function in hybrid theories.

4.1 Re-Framing Differences Among Validity Theory Authors

The long-standing divide between conceptions of validity as a property of the test itself and validity as a matter of interpretations and uses can be meaningfully reframed through the lens of function attribution and function ascription, as developed

in the philosophy of technology. Viewing validity as inherent to the test parallels a function attribution stance: it assumes that the test, by virtue of its structure and design, possesses the capacity to fulfill a defined purpose, much like a screwdriver is said to be for driving screws due to its physical properties and intended design (Kroes, 2012; Chapter 3.2). In contrast, the view that validity arises only in relation to interpretation and use corresponds to function ascription: the function (and thus validity) is not intrinsic, but is assigned based on the context of application, similar to how a rock might be ascribed the function of a paperweight under particular circumstances (Kroes, 2012; Chapter 3.4).

Both views, taken in isolation, are limited. In practice, we design tests with specific measurement goals in mind, making function attribution essential for evaluating whether the test meets the specifications of that design. However, we also routinely repurpose or reinterpret existing tests for new contexts, decisions, or populations, in which case function ascription becomes necessary to assess whether such uses are justified. To claim that validity “resides in the test” is to privilege function attribution as the full story; to focus solely on interpretations and uses is to reduce validity to function ascription. Neither approach alone captures the complex, iterative, and socially embedded nature of how tests function in practice.

Interestingly, philosophy of technology provides a compelling framework for reconciling long-standing tensions in theories of test validity by clarifying that opposing views often focus on different aspects of function. From this perspective, both are correct, but they address distinct dimensions of what it means for a test to “function.” A more comprehensive understanding of test validity, then, requires integrating these perspectives: recognizing tests as engineered artefacts with specific design intents, structural properties, and embedded use plans, while also acknowledging that validity claims must be re-evaluated when tests are repurposed, applied in new contexts, or used to support different inferential goals. In this way, test validity—much like technical function—is best understood as a hybrid concept, one that bridges the material and the intentional, the static design and the evolving use, the object and the system in which it operates.

When discussing the role of test use in validity theory, it’s important to recognize that the term

“use” itself is inherently ambiguous, encompassing multiple meanings that lead to different implications. If by “use” we refer to the purpose or intended application of a test—such as selection, diagnosis, or certification—then use is unquestionably central to validity theory. It belongs to the mind-dependent dimension of test design, aligning with theories of function that emphasize intentionality, including use plans in ICE theory. In this view, a test’s validity is inseparable from its designed purpose and the normative expectations surrounding its use. However, if by “use” we instead refer to the integration of a test into larger systems or artifacts—such as decision algorithms, school accountability frameworks, or admissions mechanisms—the implications for validity become more indirect. In such cases, concerns about validity may extend beyond the test itself. Here, any connection with further artifacts should be specified in the function requirement for a test and the validity of the test as a technical artifact should be already enough to connect validation work with that super-system. In the end, this becomes a question of technological delimitation rather than epistemology. It forces us to ask: where does the test end and the system begin? Validity work must be clear about which level of the system is being validated. While it is sufficient to validate the function of a test within its own scope, new validation requirements may emerge when the test is embedded in broader technological ecosystems. In such cases, tests may need to be reengineered to meet the functional demands of the superordinate systems they serve. Philosophy of technology thus helps us frame these challenges not as conceptual failures, but as practical questions of how to define, bound, and reconfigure technologies to meet evolving needs.

Regarding the matter of values, the study of values is essential insofar as they have the potential to block the effectiveness of a technical artifact in achieving its functional goal. For example, if we discover that a fully functional hammer emits radiation and makes the person using it sick, it doesn’t really matter if we have evidence that the hammer actually functions: it will be illegal to sell it and, thus, as a technical artifact, it will fail as such. Now, this is a less exact account of a device and may conflate the legal with the ethical. Nevertheless, a discussion of the valoric implications in the structure, use-plan, and function of the test seems to be part of a validity theory for technical artifacts.

5 A Concept of Validity from Kroes’ view about Technical Artifact Function

Kroes introduces a mode-specific distinction between two key types of proper functions: the kind-proper function and the use-proper function. These definitions offer a more precise account of how function can be understood relative to both design and use contexts. A kind-proper function is the function intended by the designer or creator of the artifact and is assigned at the moment of its creation. It, together with the physical structure of the object, determines the artifact’s membership in a technical kind—for example, an object is a screwdriver if it was made with the intention and structure appropriate for driving screws. In contrast, a use-proper function arises from actual use practices and may evolve independently of the designer’s intent. It is defined through standardized patterns of use recognized within a community of users. Thus, an artifact may acquire new use-proper functions over time without losing its original kind-proper function. This distinction is particularly useful in educational and psychological testing. A test may be designed to measure a specific construct (its kind-proper function; Moss, 2016), yet be used in contexts or for purposes not originally intended (use-proper functions). Understanding these differences helps clarify the validity debates between structuralist and contextualist interpretations of test function.

This distinction between kind-proper and use-proper functions translates directly into the domain of test validity. Under this framework, when we say that “a test is valid,” what we are really asserting is that “this artifact belongs to the function-kind of measurers of construct X.” In other words, we are making a claim about the test’s kind-proper function: that it was designed, structured, and implemented with the specific intent of measuring construct X, and that it satisfies the criteria—both functional and structural—to be considered a member of that kind. To declare that a test is valid in this mode is thus to affirm that it is a test, in the strong sense: a technical artifact whose defining function is to measure a construct under theoretically justified and operationally sound conditions. This interpretation grounds validity in the successful realization of a design, tying it to Kroes’ notion that an artifact belongs to a technical kind if it is the result of a largely correct execution of a largely correct design for that kind.

Framing test validity in this way avoids the ambiguity that often surrounds the term “valid,” by linking it explicitly to artifact kind membership rather than only to inference quality or score utility. It repositions the test not simply as a vehicle for interpretation but as a designed entity whose validity rests on its structural and intentional alignment with a measurement function.

Kroes’ mode-specific definitions of function can be directly translated into a coherent, design-based definition of test validity. Specifically, we can say:

A test intended to measure construct C is valid if and only if it belongs to the functional kind of devices that measure C— that is, if it is the result of a largely successful execution of a largely correct design for a measurer of construct C.

This definition reframes test validity as kind-membership within a class of technical artifacts defined by a measurement function. It shifts the focus from interpreting scores to evaluating whether the test, as an artifact, fulfills the criteria to be classified as a measurer of C. The test is not merely a tool that happens to generate useful interpretations; it is valid to the extent that it is, in its very structure and origin, an instantiation of the technical kind “measurer of C.” This view thus embeds validity in both the design intentions and the material realization of the test—honoring Kroes’ dual-nature framework and supporting a hybrid account of validity that integrates psychometric rigor with philosophical precision.

Several important conceptual distinctions emerge from the proposed definition of test validity as the realization of a largely correct design. Chief among these is the differentiation between a correct design and a successful implementation of a test. This distinction echoes similar bifurcations in the validity literature—for example, Zumbo’s differentiation between in-vitro and in-vivo validation, where the former focuses on how a test functions under controlled, idealized conditions, and the latter evaluates how the test behaves in real-world, ecological contexts (Zumbo, 2017). Similarly, Briggs (2004) distinguishes between design and interpretative validity, emphasizing that there is a need to validate a test before further implementation just on its design characteristics, to then later be evaluated after its actual use.

Interestingly, this “Kroesian” way of understand-

ing validity allows us to locate the realist criteria for validity as a suggested criterion for the correct design of a test rather than as a realist/causal way of attributing function. Many of the fundamental disagreements among validity theorists can be traced back to differing assumptions about what constitutes a correct design for a test. For instance, Borsboom’s view (Borsboom et al., 2004) on validity can be translated to a test being correctly designed if the construct exists and the test scores causally reflect variations in that construct. From this perspective, the core criterion for validity is ontological and causal: the test measures a real attribute and does so by virtue of a lawful connection between the attribute and the test responses.¹ In contrast, a Kroesian interpretation reframes this view not as the definition of validity itself, but as one possible account of what it means for a test to fulfill its intended function under a particular design philosophy—one grounded in scientific realism. This allows to have a realist criteria embedded in a philosophy of technology that may not be fully causal.

Mislevy’s perspective (2009), grounded in evidence-centered design, defines a correct test design as one that aligns a construct model, evidence model, and task model in a coherent evidentiary argument. Here, the test is valid not because it reveals an underlying reality, but because its components are systematically aligned to support defensible inferences about complex performances in context.

Randall’s critique (2021) pushes the conversation further by questioning the neutrality of the constructs themselves. Her work—drawing on Critical Race Theory and sociocultural perspectives—extends the very notion of what a “correct design” entails. Rather than simply accepting the construct as given, Randall invites us to scrutinize its origins, values, and exclusions. In doing so, she opens up the possibility of a more just and inclusive design, one in which constructs are redefined or expanded to reflect the phenomenological realities of diverse test-takers. This critical stance challenges traditional design assumptions and urges validity theorists to consider whether a test can be correctly

¹ Still, this Kroesian way to understand artifact-kind attribution would suggest that Borsboom’s view of validity is missing a third condition, something like “the causal relationship holds under the expected use-plans and contexts of use for the test”, symmetrical to a “largely successful implementation” of the test. With the current two conditions for existence and causality, you may only be validating the design of the test and not its implemented form.

designed if the very construct it targets is conceptually limited or socially biased.

Educational testing offers a practical yet profound insight into the limitations of declared purposes and function definitions—not just for tests, but for all technologies. While many philosophical accounts, including those in the tradition of Kroes, emphasize intentional design and functional specification, experience in test development reveals that such declarations are insufficient unless contextual boundaries are clearly articulated. This is not merely a theoretical concern but a pragmatic necessity. For instance, to claim that a knife “can cut everything” is logically falsifiable—it is possible to imagine a scenario that disproves it—but the claim is not falsifiable in practice, because it would require testing the knife against an infinite number of materials and conditions. Similarly, to claim that a test “measures construct C” in general terms is an incomplete statement unless it is accompanied by a specification of the contexts, populations, and conditions under which this measurement is expected to succeed.

This insight highlights a crucial point for any validity framework or theory of artifact function: validation requires clearly defined scope conditions. A proper definition of a test’s functional requirement must go beyond stating what the test is intended to measure—it must also specify the conditions under which that measurement is expected to succeed. This includes delineating the contexts of use, the characteristics of the intended test-taker population, the delivery environment, and any relevant constraints on administration or interpretation. Without these scope conditions, claims about a test’s validity remain too abstract to support meaningful validation efforts, and risk overlooking the situational dependencies that shape the test’s actual functioning.

In cases where a test is used for purposes beyond its original design—such as measuring a construct in a new population, or supporting decisions it was not initially intended for—we can apply Kroes’ definition of use-accidental function to understand what it means for such an interpretation and use to be valid. According to Kroes:

An agent justifiably ascribes to an artifact x the use-accidental function of being for phi-ing relative to a use plan p for x if and only if: (1) p has been assigned to x by the agent, and (2) it is both true and recognized by the agent that

there is a considerable chance that competent execution of p with x will lead to the goal of phi-ing.

Translating this to testing, we may say:

An interpretation and use of a test is valid (in the use-accidental sense) if and only if a new use plan has been assigned to the test by a user, and it is both true and recognized by the user that competent implementation of the use-plan with the test has a considerable chance of supporting the intended inference or decision.

This definition is particularly helpful for analyzing test uses that deviate from the original design yet show empirical success in new settings. For example, a college admissions test repurposed to support diagnostic feedback in schools may not have been designed for that use, but could still be considered valid if the implementation produces reliable and meaningful diagnostic information. Here, the concept of a use plan becomes essential. As articulated by Kroes, a use plan refers to the specific way in which an agent intends to use a technical artifact to achieve a particular goal. In the context of testing, the use plan complements—but is not necessarily congruent with—the original test design. While a test’s design typically includes a general specification of its intended function (e.g., to measure construct C for a given population), a use plan makes explicit how the test is to be implemented in a particular context, by whom, under what conditions, and for what immediate purpose.

This distinction is crucial for understanding test repurposing and the dynamics of emergent test uses. A test may be applied in ways not originally envisioned by its designers, guided by new or revised use plans formulated by institutions, educators, or policymakers (Moss, 2016). These plans define the expectations for the test’s role in decision-making or inference, even when the new function does not fully align with the test’s original design or prior validation evidence. Importantly, use plans are situated—they reflect the specific constraints, goals, and values of a local context—and thus provide a normative and operational lens through which function ascription and use-accidental validity can be meaningfully assessed.

In this sense, use plans serve as a conceptual bridge: they connect the artifact’s structural design to its situated function, making explicit the criteria

by which success, failure, or misfit can be judged in practice. They remind us that tests, like all socio-technical artifacts, do not operate in the abstract; their validity emerges through intentional, context-sensitive deployment—whether that deployment is aligned with, adapted from, or wholly independent of the original design.

To clarify the dual processes involved in determining test validity, I propose the following terminology:

1. **Validation** refers to the process by which we evaluate whether a test belongs to a functional kind class—that is, whether the test is the result of a largely successful execution of a largely correct design intended to measure a specific construct *C*. This process is forward-facing and design-oriented, aligning with Kroes' concept of kind-proper function, and corresponds to traditional approaches to test validation that emphasize construct representation, psychometric modeling, and alignment with intended interpretations.
2. **Retro-validation**, by contrast, refers to the process by which we justify a use plan for an existing test, particularly when the intended use deviates from or extends beyond the original design. Retro-validation evaluates whether the test, as implemented under new conditions, can be expected to support the newly ascribed function. This process corresponds to function ascription and Kroes' notion of use-accidental function, and it emphasizes empirical and practical justification over design intent.

This distinction allows us to frame validity not as a single unified claim, but as two complementary modes of justification: one focused on the artifact's original classification (validation), and the other on its evolving, contextual deployment (retro-validation). Together, they offer a more complete account of how tests operate as socio-technical artifacts whose validity must be judged both in principle and in practice.

I will also interpret the term Validation—and by extension, Retro-validation—as a forward-looking process, rather than a retrospective one. This distinction addresses a common source of confusion in validity theory, where validation is often mistakenly treated as something that happens after a test has already been used. However, in my view,

understanding the function of a test only after its deployment misses the core purpose of validation, which is to justify its anticipated use and ensure it is fit for its intended function. For retrospective inquiries—those concerned with how a test has functioned in practice—I will instead use the term Evaluation, reserving Evaluation and Retro-evaluation to refer to post hoc studies of functional attribution (what the test did) and functional ascription (what the test was supposed to do). This terminological distinction allows for greater conceptual clarity, aligning validation with the design and planning phase, and evaluation with the assessment of past performance, in both technical and normative terms.

Ultimately, I propose to understand validity as a theory of artifact functioning—a conceptual framework for evaluating whether the ensemble of devices, processes, and representations that constitute a test function successfully, either through the realization of a correct design or through a justified adaptation to new uses. This perspective treats a test not as a singular object, but as a composite socio-technical system, composed of multiple interdependent artifacts: test items, scoring algorithms, delivery platforms, proctoring protocols, and interpretive guidelines, among others.

I further understand this concept as self-similar: the validity of any component device within the larger system can itself be evaluated in terms of whether it is (a) a largely successful implementation of a largely correct design, or (b) a retro-validated use of an existing artifact repurposed for a new function. For example, a machine-learning algorithm embedded in a test scoring system must be validated in the same terms—by asking whether its operation fulfills a design intended to support meaningful inference, or whether its use can be justified under a use plan that was not foreseen during its original development.

This recursive approach enables a layered and systemic analysis of validity, accommodating both traditional psychometric constructs and emerging technological components within a unified theoretical framework. It extends the notion of test validity beyond score interpretation, toward a broader inquiry into the functionality, interoperability, and ethical justifiability of all artifacts involved in test delivery and interpretation.

6 From Construct Misrepresentation to Test Malfunction

Kroes' distinctions between proper and accidental use of technical artifacts offer a powerful lens for rethinking the concept of test invalidity. Traditionally, discussions of invalidity in educational and psychological testing have centered on issues such as construct underrepresentation, construct-irrelevant variance, or flawed score interpretations. However, by adopting Kroes' framework, we can expand the vocabulary of invalidity to include failures of artifact function—not only in terms of psychometric shortcomings, but also in relation to mismatches between design, use plans, and actual deployment. In this view, a test may be invalid not merely because it fails to measure what it claims, but because it has been malfunctioned, dysfunctioned, or misused—intentionally or accidentally—relative to its design or to a newly ascribed function. This opens space for a richer classification of test failures that moves beyond the score level to consider the roles, expectations, and technical-operational integrity of all devices involved in the testing process.

At this point, we can identify three critical moving parts in the life of a test: the correct design, the intended design, and the actual implementation. The correct design refers to the theoretically and empirically sound structure required for a test to fulfill its function—what the test ought to be, based on best practices, valid construct representation, and defensible measurement models. The intended design reflects the test developer's own design decisions and assumptions—what they believe the test should do, how it should function, and how it is structured to support those goals. Finally, the implementation refers to how the test is actually realized and delivered in practice, including item construction, administration procedures, scoring, and interpretation.

For example, a test may be a faithful implementation of its intended design, but the design itself may be flawed. This is often the case when constructs are rooted in dominant cultural frameworks—such as whiteness or narrow socio-economic assumptions—that exclude or marginalize alternative ways of knowing and being. In such cases, the failure is not in implementation but in the intended design itself. Conversely, a test developer may intentionally address these issues in the design stage—embedding inclusive construct definitions and equitable measurement principles—yet the test

may still fail in practice, for instance during item writing or task development, by reintroducing biases or overlooking critical elements of the design intent.

These observations motivate a more fine-grained vocabulary for test malfunction, based on gaps between the three moving parts of test validity: correct design, intended design, and implementation.

1. **Test dysfunction** refers to a gap between the correct design and the intended design—that is, when the developer's conceptualization of the test departs from what would be considered theoretically or ethically sound.
2. **Test malfunction** refers to a gap between the intended design and the implementation—when the test is built or delivered in a way that fails to realize its own design goals.
3. I propose the term **test parafunction** to describe cases where a function is achieved in accordance with the intended design, but this function does not correspond to the correct design of the test.
4. **Test hyperfunction** refers to functions achieved by the implemented test beyond what was anticipated in the intended design, whether beneficial or harmful.
5. **Test refunction** describes instances where an implemented test deviates from its intended design but in a way that moves closer to the correct design—effectively correcting or improving upon the original intent through practice.

Figure 1 explains the different concepts outlined here to refer to test malfunction.

This taxonomy expands the conceptual space of validity by allowing us to describe not only failures but also emergent reinterpretations and unexpected alignments—recognizing that test functioning is dynamic, distributed, and contextually situated.

All of the preceding concepts contribute to a richer and more differentiated framework for understanding test invalidity. The traditional dual categories of construct underrepresentation and construct-irrelevant variance—while foundational in mainstream validity theory—tend to conflate issues related to both design and implementation, without clearly articulating where the failure originates. These categories are useful diagnostic tools

but often lack the granularity needed to distinguish between flaws in the theoretical blueprint of the test (design) and problems that emerge in practical realization (implementation).

Within this expanded framework, test dysfunction—the misalignment between a correct and an intended design—emerges as a particularly under-theorized form of invalidity. Despite its profound implications, it has received limited attention in the traditional literature on validity. It is primarily critical scholars who have foregrounded this dimension, pushing the field to adopt more stringent and inclusive criteria for what counts as a "correct" test design. These perspectives demand scrutiny not only of psychometric models, but of the cultural, political, and epistemological assumptions embedded in construct definitions themselves. By explicitly naming and theorizing dysfunction, we begin to hold tests accountable not just for how well they are implemented, but for what they are designed to do—and for whom.

7 Implications for the use of Artificial Intelligence in Educational and Psychological Measurement

One direct implication of this artifact-based approach to validity is that it provides a robust rationale for evaluating non-test components that play critical roles within larger technological systems where a test is embedded. In modern educational and psychological measurement, tests rarely operate in isolation—they are increasingly integrated into complex socio-technical ecosystems involving automated scoring engines, adaptive delivery platforms, biometric proctoring tools, AI-based item generation, and dynamic user interfaces. This framework makes clear that every component in such a system—whether it qualifies as a "test" in the traditional sense or not—must be subject to validity scrutiny. Specifically, each device or subsystem must either (1) be the result of a largely correct design aligned with the measurement goals of the system, or (2) be justified through a retro-validated use plan that accounts for its function, limitations, and contextual deployment.

This concern becomes particularly salient in the context of Artificial Intelligence. When we train an AI model specifically for use within a testing system—for example, to score written responses, select items, or monitor test-taker behavior—we are not just developing software; we are design-

ing a functional component of a larger measurement device. As such, we must evaluate both the correctness of the design—is the model theoretically and ethically appropriate for the role it is assigned?—and the correctness of its implementation—does it perform reliably and consistently in practice under the intended conditions? On the other hand, when we adopt a pre-existing AI model (e.g., a large language model or a pretrained image classifier), the situation shifts: we must engage in retro-validation, constructing a new use plan that justifies the repurposing of the model within the testing context. We cannot assume that the model's original function transfers cleanly to our measurement goals; instead, we must ask whether the new function can be justified based on how the model performs in its new role.

8 Conclusions

The philosophy of technology offers a compelling and much-needed perspective on validity theory. By shifting the focus from abstract epistemological debates to the functional realities of artifacts, it allows us to reconceptualize tests not merely as instruments for inferring traits or abilities, but as socio-technical artifacts—intentional constructions embedded in material, institutional, and cultural systems. This acknowledgment is of critical importance: it repositions validity as a question not only of score interpretation but of artifact functionality—that is, whether a test and its surrounding technologies do what they are meant to do, for whom, and under what conditions. Understanding tests in this way opens new pathways for both critique and design, pushing us to examine not just whether a test produces reliable data, but whether it has been correctly conceptualized, justifiably repurposed, and responsibly implemented within its broader system of use.

While this paper has focused primarily on the technical and functional dimensions of tests as artifacts, it is important to recognize that the "social" in socio-technical is not a peripheral consideration—it is foundational to any meaningful theory of test validity. Tests are not just designed and used; they are interpreted, governed, contested, and lived within social systems. Their legitimacy depends on the trust of stakeholders, their use is shaped by institutional policies and power dynamics, and their consequences are felt differently across populations. The validation of a test, then, cannot be complete

without attending to its social embeddedness: Who defines the construct? Whose knowledge systems are legitimized or excluded? Who benefits—or is harmed—by the ways tests function? Although our main emphasis has been on functional alignment and design logic, future work must further develop this framework to integrate social theories of power, equity, and justice, ensuring that the validation of socio-technical artifacts is not only technically sound, but also socially accountable.

Perhaps paradoxically, the question of what counts as “the test” is more foundational than the question of how to validate it. In many ways, validity begins with boundary work: deciding what devices, systems, and interactions are to be included under the concept of “the test.” Once we acknowledge that a test is a socio-technical artifact, not just a psychometric instrument, validity becomes a matter of determining whether that artifact—or any of its components—can legitimately be considered a latent measurer, whether by design (proper use) or by recontextualization (accidental use).

Within this broader view, construct validity remains central. It offers a normative and methodological basis for what constitutes a correct design of a measurement device. Construct validity is not only about psychometric integrity; it anchors the general functionality of the test both within and beyond its originally envisioned contexts. This relevance becomes especially clear when we consider time-contingent shifts, such as those induced by the COVID-19 pandemic. Such events underscore that all tests operate in moving contexts, where interpretations and uses must be continuously re-evaluated. A purely pragmatic approach risks overfitting tests to narrow, ephemeral situations, undermining their durability and ethical coherence. This is why revalidation—the ongoing justification of new use plans—is not an exception, but a core part of test maintenance and responsibility.

The longstanding debate over whether validity is a property of the test itself or of its interpretations and uses reflects a legitimate and enduring tension—one that also emerges in philosophical discussions of function attribution. It parallels the distinction between proper and accidental uses, and the philosophical differentiation between kind-function (what something is designed to do) and ascribed function (what it ends up doing in practice). From the perspective of validity as a theory of artifact functioning, validity is inherently context-dependent, situated, and provisional. It is not a

fixed property embedded in a test but rather a dynamic process of inquiry and learning—learning what the test can do, for whom, and under which conditions. Whether a test is used as originally intended or repurposed for new aims, its validity hinges on the articulation of a coherent theory: a theory about how a socio-technical artifact functions within varied contexts and for diverse users in the specific domain of educational and psychological measurement. Therefore, both perspectives—realist and pragmatic—are not only possible but mutually necessary. A purely causal view, such as that proposed by Borsboom, may help specify conditions for a correct design but neglects the role of use-plans and the importance of successful implementation. Conversely, a purely pragmatic view, as in Kane’s argument-based approach, emphasizes justification and interpretive coherence but often leaves underdeveloped the question of what constitutes a correct design in the first place. Validity arguments for educational and psychological tests should ideally address three interconnected elements: (1) why the proposed structure of the test is correct, (2) why the use-plan, in conjunction with that structure, constitutes a correct design, and (3) how the actual implementation of that design can be defensibly anticipated. These components are crucial for a comprehensive validation framework, yet they are rarely made explicit in practice, even within implementations of the argument-based approach.

One of the most compelling contributions of this new way of thinking about validity theory is that it offers a coherent and transferable rationale for the validation of artifacts beyond traditional tests. For instance, in the field of Test Security, systems of prevention, deterrence, and detection can be evaluated not only based on their current effectiveness, but also in terms of their ideal design, structural coherence, and fidelity of implementation. The conceptual elements discussed throughout this paper—structure, use-plan, and function—translate naturally into this broader class of assessment-related devices, which, though not tests per se, are essential components within the larger ecosystem of assessment technologies.

The definitions provided here for validity may sound rather obvious in some way. Still, I believe their simplicity is helpful to identify aspects many times forgotten in Test Development and Validation: the need to document the design of a test and the rationale for why this is a correct design, the

need to document the use plan of a test for both validation and retro-validation, and the conditions to declare a sufficiently successful implementation of a test. The separation of a realist view on a philosophy of technology and a realist view on a correct design of a test also can help to reconcile this inherent contradiction in tests: as tools are mind-dependent, but the constructs they try to measure may be mind-independent.

I hope this connection with the philosophy of technology inspires practitioners to explore this emerging field more deeply—one that holds firm promise for educational and psychological measurement. Not only does it bring new conceptual tools for understanding tests as socio-technical artifacts, but it also helps us recognize that many validity theorists have, perhaps inadvertently, been laying the groundwork for a principled theory of socio-technical artifact validation all along. By reframing their contributions in this light, we can both honor their legacy and open new pathways for more rigorous, inclusive, and context-aware approaches to validation.

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Figure 1: Explanation for a Taxonomy of Test Malfunction